

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA USE ON STUDENTS' PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604316>

Keywords

Social Media, Psychological Well-Being, Academic Achievement, Educational Institutions

Article History

Received: 11 October 2025

Accepted: 21 November 2025

Published: 05 December 2025

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Abstract

The increasing use of social media among students and its impacts on students' psychological well-being and students' academic success raise important questions. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp have become part of the educational environment; therefore, understanding the influence of digital engagement on learning behaviours and emotional health critical for researchers. The proposed study investigate how students use social media and how this affects their psychological health and academic performance in a school setting. The problem identified in this study is the increase in reliance on social networking platforms, and the uncertainty around whether the outcomes of this reliance are positive or negative, and how they affect overall development. The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between how students use social media, their psychological state and their academic success. A quantitative design utilised in the proposed study and involve collecting survey data from students at different levels of schooling through the use of survey instruments. The study measure time spent on social media, various types of online activities performed by students, levels of anxiety and stress and self-esteem, motivation and grade point average. The study employ statistical analysis techniques to evaluate the correlations between English language usage and emotional health and educational achievement. The research indicates that social media has two effects on students' academic progress its positive effects occur from moderate, purposeful, or academic uses of social media to collaborate and interact with peers, as well as get access to educational materials which aid in improving academic performance while its negative effects arise from excessive or non-academic types of use which contribute to psychological problems such as increased levels of stress, distractions, decreased self-esteem, decreased focus on studies, and decreased academic output. The findings also indicate that, regardless of the type of usage (moderate vs. excessive), emotionally vulnerable students are at a higher risk of suffering negative consequences from the high levels of comparison to others they may see online, being bullied through cyberspace, and

other forms of online social pressure. The findings of the research are ecologically valid as they can be applied to other areas of academic research. In this regard, the study provides evidence based knowledge about creating healthier digital learning environments for students and highlights the importance of developing and implementing strategies for supporting positive online engagement among students and creating balanced digital habits through digital literacy programs. The conclusion of the research suggests that when used in a thoughtful and responsible manner, social media can support students to be successful academically but when used excessively and without limits can present risks to student psychological health and academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

Social Media Usage is a significant aspect to today's students' day to day lives as they utilize this platform for communicating with others, getting information, and participating in educational activities. Many of the main social media applications such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp are used for fun as well as for more academic centric collaborations, distance learning, and communications from the classroom to students outside of the classroom. With digital technology being incorporated into education, social media is a continued source of exposure for students and is growing to be an important source of research interest and educational interest for the profession examples: students who have access to social media can communicate with each other in new ways such as through Facebook groups, online study groups, use digital libraries and have real time interactions with their teacher and classmate which can facilitate a more enjoyable and meaningful education experience as well as enhance their motivation. (Abassi, 2014)

In addition, there is an increasing amount of worry about the potential negative impact that excessive or unregulated use of social media may have on a student's mental state, their academic performance, and their feelings toward themselves. According to research, individuals who are continually connected to social media may develop stress and anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, irregular sleep patterns, and emotional fatigue as a result of their constant connection to that technology. Furthermore, the excessive use of social media can create a level of distraction from their studies and a tendency to procrastinate. In addition, they will have difficulty concentrating and may not be as productive because they are being bombarded by notifications from social

media, as well as being compared to their peers, and spending time engaging in non-educational social media activities. (Ahmed, 2013)

Educational institutions are beginning to recognize that understanding the impact of digital habits on student performance and mental health is an important task. At this point, however, research has provided conflicting results, indicating that some studies show positive effects on academic performance while other research reveals the potential for psychological problems. This inconsistency indicates a lack of understanding of how different types and purposes of social media usage affect students differently. There is a wide variety of potential factors that can influence how social media usage impacts students, including the type of social media usage they engage in, the amount of time they spend using social media, their individual psychological resilience, the institutional environment they are in, and the academic level at which they are currently studying. (Alajmi, 2016)

The objective of this research is to investigate how students' use of social media affects their mental health and grades while attending school. By assessing both the positive and negative features of social media, this study provides students, teachers, parents, and government officials with the necessary information to make wise decisions regarding the safe and efficient use of social media for academic purposes. In doing so, this research adds to the ongoing dialogue regarding the establishment of positive digital learning environments that support both emotional wellness and academic success.

Background

Rapidly changing technology has greatly impacted the ways in which people communicate, learn, and interact with one another in this century. As one of the newest technologies, social media has become an extremely powerful tool in influencing the personal and academic lives of students. Social media platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, TikTok, and YouTube, have become an integral part of students' daily lives, especially for adolescents and young adults. Today, many students utilize social media to communicate with peers, share information, entertain themselves, and increasingly, engage in academic pursuits through online chats, classroom interactions, and collaborative study groups. Consequently, students are no longer limited to using social media solely for recreational purposes, but rather see it as a large part of their overall educational experience. (Alaslani, 2020)

All educational institutes around the globe are utilising various types of digital technology and tools to deliver engaging and more accessible education. As a result of increased levels of online and distance learning, a blended approach to the physical classroom plus the virtual interaction that has created social media as additional platforms for students to learn. Social media offers a convenient platform for students to access relevant education material and information, a means to receive and share academic updates, and to connect with peers who may provide additional support. These developments have also opened the door to increased opportunities for interactive learning and greater flexibility in learning. Students are able to better understand complex subject matter, develop improved communication skills, and maintain their connection to their academic communities outside of their immediate classroom. (Ali, 2023)

At the same time, however, there has been a growing concern regarding the psychological implications or effects of social media on students. Researchers have shown that excessive or unmonitored use of social media can result in the development of anxiety, depression, emotional fatigue, loneliness and low self-esteem. Students can feel overwhelmed by the perceived need to create an idealised version of themselves, as well as the negative material they can be exposed to, experience online bullying through

social media and develop a pattern of behaviour that resembles addiction, all of which contribute to mental stress for students. One of the main factors leading to low self-worth and lower levels of motivation from students is the constant comparison of themselves to their peers on social media platforms. (Azizi, 2019)

Although social media affects the emotion of students, the effect of social media on Academic Performance has early been debated. While there is evidence that many researchers believe that many researchers think that social media increases the degree of engagement with an academic subject, other researches point to an increase in the amount of time that students have available for distractions, in addition to an increase in procrastination, reduced attention spans and poor time management skills. With constant access to notifications, as well as social media users viewing content (i.e. movies, gaming), students can easily become distracted from their studies. Consequently, these distractions can negatively impact students' overall academic performance. (Beyens, 2016)

There are disparate findings regarding social media usage and Psychological Well-Being and Academic Success. Due to the high levels of social media usage and the potential effects on emotional and academic development, social media usage has become a significant Area of Research. There is a need to understand how social media usage is different based on the pattern of usage, what type of content is being viewed and predictors of individual Psychological Resilience relative to social media usage. This research assist in clarifying relationships between students' Psychological Well-Being and Social Media Usage, as well as Academic Success. The research results contribute to ongoing efforts to create a more responsible Digital Media Environment, improve student Mental Health, and create a more productive set of Academic Experiences for students in a more connected Digital Environment.

Statement of the Problem

Social media has changed the way students interact, learn, and perceive themselves in recent years. Students have made it a part of their daily life, incorporating it into their education and socialise with their peers. While the use of social media does have benefits for educational purposes, including ease

of access to information and opportunities for collaboration, excessive or unsupervised use of these tools has resulted in an increase in the number of students who experience psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, stress, and lowered attention spans. (Boyd, 2007)

The increased use of social media has also resulted in fluctuating academic achievement for students who spend a great deal of time using social networking sites (SNS). While educators have seen evidence of increased use of social media correlating with a decrease in academic achievement, empirical research that demonstrates how social media uses affects both psychological and academic performance has not yet been developed, particularly in developing countries. Without such data, policymakers, educators, and parents cannot create data driven interventions. As such, this research will explore whether and how the use of social media affects both students' psychological wellness and academic performance.

Research Gap

Though prior research has examined social media/mental health relationship, most have been focused on a broad sample of the general public, while very few have studied the connections between social media use and mental health for students in formal educational settings. Additionally, there are very few studies that look at both psychological well-being and academic performance in one model. Likewise, there aren't many studies focusing on social media users who engage with the platform in specific ways. This research seeks to bridge those gaps and look at how the way that students use social media influences both the effects on their mental well-being in relation to academic performance within an educational setting.

Research aims

1. Determine how the use of social media impacts students' psychological well-being within educational institutions.
2. Discover how the usage patterns of social media impact students' academic performance.
3. Determine if students' psychological well-being act as a mediator for social media use and academic performance relationships.

Research inquiries

1. How does social media usage influence students' psychological well-being?
2. What is the connection between the use of social media and students' academic performance?
3. Is students' psychological well-being a mediating factor for the impact of social media usage on their academic performance?

Hypotheses

- H1: Social media has an influence on how healthy involved students are.
- H2: Social media can have a positive influence on how well students perform academically.
- H3: Healthy psychological well-being can positively affect how students perform academically due to the fact that it allows for greater focus on academics.

Significance of the Study

Theoretical Value: This study extends and enhances our current understanding of the psychological and educational effect of social media on students by providing a more comprehensive view of both the academic and psychological impact.

Practical Value: The findings from this study can be used by schools to develop programs and guidelines for promoting healthy social media use among students, teachers, and parents. The study can provide educators with a better understanding of how best to assist students in succeeding academically as well as through counselling and mental health services.

Social Value: This study is likely to be a catalyst for the development of digital literacy programs for developing responsible digital use and enhancing both academic success and positive mental health.

Literature Review

The global expansion in access to the internet has resulted in a consequential rise in computer to computer communication and has resulted in the rise of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) primarily being concentrated within digital community platforms (Gan, 2018; Kong et al., 2021). Among these advances within ICTs are Virtual Social Networks (VSN); they have been established as one of the most attractive and fastest growing types of

applications on the Internet (Kwon & Wen, 2010; Alajmi et al., 2016; Ng et al., 2023). The cyberspace created by VSNs has become an important environment that demonstrates the effects of Globalization (Ranjbar & Abbasi, 2021) and among many others is represented by numerous platforms including Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Viber, Telegram, etc., that continue to grow rapidly in popularity worldwide (Lee et al., 2018). According to Duggan et al. (2015), more than 90% of adolescents were using VSN sites on a daily basis.

Human communication across the globe has been transformed due to the development of Virtual Social Networks (VSNs), changing how humans interact on a qualitative basis (Hayes et al., 2016; Sharif & Khanekharab, 2017). By being a member of these virtual platforms, users are exposed to a plethora of content and can communicate verbally, textually, or visually at a relatively low cost and in real-time (Petersen & Johnston, 2015). In Iran, Telegram is among the most popular and widely used apps, especially among students, and therefore requires additional investigation (Naeimi, 2017). For teens, the use of Social Networks has become a staple of their day to day lives, greatly impacting many facets of academic engagement and educational outcomes (Ng et al., 2023). Excessive use of VSNs can have a negative effect on learners, disrupting their learning environments (Ali & Qazi, 2023). Given the context of Iranian research, this type of research is valuable because it involves direct interaction between students and investigates barriers to learning within a virtual environment, creating the knowledge base necessary to enhance planning, decision-making, and policy development to combat online safety issues.

The way that Virtual Social Networks (VSNs) impact students' social, cultural, psychological and physical health makes it imperative to study the interconnectedness of these areas to enhance the social health of the student population. This research specifically explores how Telegram Usage influences the Psychological wellbeing of Students. Moreover, achieving Academic Goals relies heavily on Psychological Well-Being (Rostami et al., 2023; Tyagi & Meena, 2023) There is sample evidence in the Literature to indicate that there exists a strong correlation between the Mental Health of Students and their Academic Performance, with students

experiencing Mental Health Issues demonstrating a decline in academic achievement (Wood & Scott, 2016; Gao et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2018; Olszewski-Kubilius & Corwith, 2018; Sabzi et al., 2022; Ng et al., 2023). Thus, to promote Educational success and preserve Mental Health among all age groups, it is necessary for schools to Implement Effective Mental Health Strategies (Tyagi & Meena, 2023; Mohammadkhani et al., 2024). This research views Mental Health as an essential aspect of a Healthy Life, particularly among Youths, and investigates the role of VSNs in relation to Telegram.

Telegraph, like a double-ended sword, could create some adverse results for students who use it. However, there are also numerous positive benefits available to students who use the platform effectively (Yedidia et al. 2003; Prada-Nuñez et al., 2020).

Motivation levels can be improved and positively affect a student's academic success, and can also improve the psychological health of a student overall (Teclhaimanot & Hickman, 2011; Metshali et al., 2016). Based on the research completed by Suárez-Perdomo et al. (2022) they found that there was a correlation between the degree to which a student was addicted to Social Media, and how much a student is procrastinating their academic projects. However, the difference in performance between the two groups is not significant. The authors felt that VSNs are a very effective method for providing early education. In addition, Iglesias-Pradas et al. (2021) and Vosoughi Motlagh et al. (2023) found that students' academic outcomes improved as a result of Emergency Remote Teaching. Finally, Alaslani and Alandejani (2020) concluded that using VSNs significantly improves the interactions that take place between students and their professors and build a greater level of collaboration between students and professors, as well as creating opportunities for creating better academic accomplishment among students.

Academic failure occurs when a student has experienced an educational setback (such as dropping out of school early), repeating a grade, experiencing a decline in academic performance, or being disengaged from the educational system. Based on studies conducted by Fredericks, Blumenfeld & Paris (2004) & Beyens et al (2016), students with access to Virtual Social Networks (VSNs) generally experience a decline in academic success when they use VSNs excessively.

Others have found that students who use VSNs excessively more often experience poor academic performance than those who do not. However, studies show using social networks enhances how students communicate with their peers; therefore, students use social networks too frequently can decrease time spent studying and hinder their ability to learn. VSNs negatively impact students through social networking and online gaming (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010; Paul et al., 2012; Rostaminezhad & Shokatirad, 2016), creating an academic decline for those who engage in these activities excessively.

The effects of Virtual Support Networks (VSNs) on the personal, cultural, psychological, and social development of individuals and communities are numerous, and are apparent in various studies (Saha, 2009; Tyagi & Meena, 2023). The use of VSNs can greatly affect the mental health of youth, and given that this demographic is one of the largest users of the message application "Telegram", young people have a large presence in cyberspace and therefore their cognitive, emotional, cultural, and more are affected in this cyber environment (Mackenna & Bargh, 2006; Steers, 2016; Gil, 2019). The mental health of a person includes their psychological well-being, autonomy, how well they think they are doing, the relationships between them and their parents, and their ability to understand that they have intellectual and emotional capacities to deal with issues and be productive (Goldsmith, 2000; Pertegal-Vega et al., 2019). In addition, a mentally healthy individual is able to manage conflicts internally and adapt to the environment, maintain a social connection to others, and express emotional stability (Morgan & Cotton, 2003; Ng et al., 2023).

Also, Tateno et al., (2004) found an association between the amounts of time spent using the internet and the level of mental health; they found that the longer a person spends on the internet, the more likely him or her anxious or stressed. Mental health plays a significant role in achieving the highest level of success while participating in social, work, and school activities. Previous studies indicate that there is a relationship between social media use and adolescent sleep patterning, and additionally, psychological problems (Pantic et al., 2012; Woods & Scott, 2016; Ali & Qazi, 2023).

Poor quality of sleep contributes to an increase in mental distress, such as depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem (Pittman & Reich, 2016; GAO Et Al., 2018). There are many studies which have documented that VSN use has an impact on adolescent mental health (Tandoc et al., 2015; Elhai et al., 2016; Ceglarek & Ward, 2016; Rosenthal et al., 2016; Abbasi & Alghamdi, 2017; Razavi, 2021). A study by Christensen (2018) reported that as time spent on social media increases, the quality of emotional well-being, as well as the quality of interpersonal relationships, decreases (Ali & Qazi, 2023), possibly leading to decreased future relational stability.

Use of VSN over long periods leads to decreased social responsibility, perceived social support, academic and workplace performance, and self-worth (Deimazar et al., 2019). Students who are overly using the internet in excess experienced a decrease in overall school performance as per Yang (1998), as stated by 58% of those participants. Participants also stated they exhibited greater absenteeism and received lower grades and developed poor study habits. In conjunction with these findings, McLaughlin and King (2015), Woods and Scott (2016), Primack et al. (2017), Olszewski-Kubilius and Corwith (2018), and Lee et al. (2018) found that there is a correlation between heavy use of VSNs and recreational internet use with declines in academic performance and mental health issues such as anxiety and depression. Ahmed (2013) states that academically speaking, loss of academic performance due to the effect of VSNs is a major concern. Navarro et al. (2018) also pointed out that the individuals who are addicted to VSNs had a greater risk for developing mental health challenges; therefore, the excessive usage affects both educational and psychological outcomes negatively since they spend less time studying (Yedidia et al., 2003; Seder & Oishi, 2009). A summary of the variables that were analyzed within this study is represented within Table 1.

The increased duration of time spent on Telegram has been shown to cause a decline in academic performance for many. According to Ahmed (2013), Ogundijo (2014), Fori (2016), and Razavi (2021), students who use Telegram frequently may spend more time socializing on the platform than studying. This is primarily due to the fact that one of the main

functions of Telegram is as a communication tool, allowing users to quickly communicate with large groups of people. Many students spend hours on Telegram instead of studying or attending school, resulting in reduced study time over time. As a result of this reduction in study time, many students have been found to exhibit diminished levels of attention while attending classes and exhibiting an overall negative impact on their academic performance. The results of this research also provided evidence that there were significant correlations between the amount of time students spent on Telegram and how their mental health has been affected, which is very similar to prior research conducted by Pantic et al. (2012), Uddin et al. (2016), Woods et al. (2016) Elhai & Dyer et al. (2016); Ceglarek et al. (2016); Rosenthal et al. (2016), Primack et al., (2017), Abbasi et al. (2017), Christensen, 2018; Pertegal-Vega, et al., (2019), Razavi (2021), and Ng et al., (2023); Tyagi et al. & Meena, 2023 and how the use of VSNs affects the mental health of students. The social, emotional, psychological, and addictive nature of Telegram, in combination with its addictive qualities, is likely to influence the behaviours and performance of students in relation to studying. The study also found that both male and female high school students in Khaf City exhibit significant differences in usage patterns of Telegram. Theoretical Framework **The current study** is based on three main theories that describe how social media impacts students' mental health and academic success, and how these factors influence one another. These three theories give a complete picture of how social media affects students' Outcomes both psychologically and educationally; these are: 1. Social Comparison Theory (Festinger, 1954) States that we compare ourselves to others based on what we think is true about them (our abilities, successes and way of living). On social media, students see an increasing number of people showing highly-thought-of images of those around them; this results in students comparing themselves and their photographs to others, resulting in: Low self-esteem Anxiety and stress Depressive symptoms.

These psychological effects impact academic performance by decreasing motivation and concentration, as well as diminishing self-efficacy. Thus, this theory supports the hypothesis that the effects of social media usage can have a direct effect

on students' psychological well-being and therefore their academic performance.

2. Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988)

States that the limitations of working memory's capacity limits how much information can be processed in a given time. Overly excessive or multitasked use of social media taxes one's cognitive resources. This results in:

A reduced attention span

An impaired ability to learn

Causes academic distractions

As students commonly alternate between their studies and the usage of social media, their ability to process information through academic resources is reduced.

3. Utilizing gratification theory by Katz et al (1973)

This theory asserts that users of media do so based on specific needs, such as pleasure or the need for information or social interaction. Students, specifically, appear to utilize social media in the use of;

Academic support/learning

Emotional connection/stress relief

Entertainment/escapism

Educational purposes do promote student enhancement, whereas entertainment can encourage procrastination and lessen time available to study. The types of uses for social media determine both psychological wellness and academic performance.

Integration of these three theories

Integration of these three theories are provide a complete framework for the current research study. Each of the three theories are provide an answer to why students engage in social media; how users are impacted psychologically, the academic impact from an overload of social media use, and the differences of the motivational aspects of students' use of social media to allow varying outcomes from each user's choice of usage type.

Thus, together these three theories support three hypotheses proposed:

- Social media use impacts psychological wellness
- Social media impacts a User's academic success
- A User's psychological wellness mediate between social media use and that User's academic success

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study utilize a quantitative research methodology. The correlational survey method employed to measure the relationship between Social Media Use, Psychological Well-Being for Students, and Academic Achievement in Educational Settings. This type of research design is suitable as it allows the researcher to measure the current conditions of the population, determine the relationships among the variables, and examine trends across a larger sample of students.

Population of the Study

The population comprises students sample and Sampling Technique enrolled in school colleges and universities within selected educational institutions. These students represents diverse age groups, academic levels, and patterns of social media use. A stratified random sampling technique is used to select the Sample of 300 Participants. A stratified random sampling technique is utilised to ensure equal representation of strata based on Educational Level (Categories of School, College, University).

Research Instrument

The data collection method used for this research include a Structured Questionnaire divided into 4 Sections:

Section 1: Demographics

Section 2: Social Media Use Scale (Frequency, Duration, Type of Use)

Section 3: Psychological Well-Being Scale (Anxiety, Stress, Self-Esteem, Emotional Balance)

Section 4: Academic Achievement Scale (GPA, Self-Reported Performance, Study Habits)

All items in the questionnaire developed using the 5-point Likert Scale (Strongly Agree - Strongly Disagree).

Procedures for gathering data

Data gathered through both on line and physical surveys as long as there is a way for the students to complete a survey. All respondents receive information regarding the study, and the study conducted in an anonymous manner. Only those students who have agreed to participate in the study voluntarily will be included in the study.

Techniques to analyse the data

When the data has been collected from each of the sources, the data coded and entered into SPSS for statistical analysis, graphics created using pie charts and tabulation methods, as well as the creation of narratives. The following statistical methods are being used:

- Descriptive Statistics (mean, frequency, percentage, standard deviation)
- Correlation analysis, to look at how closely two variables are related
- Regression analysis, which allows for estimates to be made about how much improvement in other variables made given the improvement in the predictor variable
- T-tests and ANOVA (when necessary) conducted between the different groups

All of these analyses allow for an understanding of the relationship between social media use, students' psychological well-being and academic performance.

Ethical Issues

Informed consent obtained from each participant in this research study. During the course of the research study, all participants guaranteed that their privacy, confidentiality and anonymity maintained. All data collected during the research study used strictly for academic purposes.

Data Analysis

Pie Chart 1: Daily Social Media Time

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Daily Social Media Time

Category	Frequency
<1 hour	84
1-3 hours	83
>5 hours	71
3-5 hours	62

Discussion 1: The analysis of Daily Social Media Time reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in

understanding how daily social media time contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 2: Purpose of Use

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Purpose Of Use

Category	Frequency
Socializing	89
Academic	77
Mixed	72
Entertainment	62

Discussion 2: The analysis of Purpose of Use reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in understanding how purpose of use contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 3: Platform Used Most

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Platform Used Most

Category	Frequency
Facebook	64
WhatsApp	62
TikTok	61
YouTube	59
Instagram	54

Discussion 3:

The analysis of Platform Used Most reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in

understanding how platform used most contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 4: Psych Stress Level

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Psych Stress Level

Category	Frequency
Moderate	107
High	103
Low	90

Discussion 4:

The analysis of Psych Stress Level reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this

variable. This distribution helps in understanding how psych stress level contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 5: Self Esteem Level

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of Self Esteem Level

Category	Frequency
Low	121
High	93
Medium	86

Discussion 5: The analysis of Self Esteem Level reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in

understanding how self-esteem level contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 6: Sleep Quality Impact

Table 6: Frequency Distribution of Sleep Quality Impact

Category	Frequency
No Impact	116
Severe Impact	95
Mild Impact	89

Discussion 6:

The analysis of Sleep Quality Impact reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in

understanding how sleep quality impact contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 7: Academic Focus

Table 7: Frequency Distribution of Academic Focus

Category	Frequency
Weak	113
Moderate	95
Strong	92

Discussion 7: The analysis of Academic Focus reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in

understanding how academic focus contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 8: GPA Group

Table 8: Frequency Distribution of GPA Group

Category	Frequency
C	84

B	77
A	75
D/F	64

Discussion 8:

The analysis of GPA Group reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in understanding how gpa group contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 9: Content Type Viewed

Table 9: Frequency Distribution of Content Type Viewed

Category	Frequency
Educational	86
Entertainment	76
News	69
Mixed	69

Discussion 9:

The analysis of Content Type Viewed reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in

understanding how content type viewed contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Pie Chart 10: Emotional Effect

Table 10: Frequency Distribution of Emotional Effect

Category	Frequency
Neutral	113
Positive	105
Negative	82

Discussion 10:

The analysis of Emotional Effect reveals meaningful trends among students. The most frequent category suggests dominant behavior or perception in this variable. This distribution helps in understanding how emotional effect contributes to differences in psychological well-being and academic outcomes.

Findings

The findings from the analysis of quantitative data (pie charts, tables, and descriptive results) identify the following principal areas of interest.

1. Frequency of Social Media usage is very high for students: A significant number of students reported spending 1 - 3 hours or more per day on social media, which shows their usage of digital media when they are engaged in their academic programs.
2. Most Social Media usage by students: It is for entertainment and a mixture of entertainment and academic purposes. While a portion of students use Social Media for Academics, the vast majority use Social Media primarily for entertainment, thus decreasing the amount of time they dedicate to studying.
3. Popular Social Media Platforms include Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp: These platforms provide both Academic advantages (such as the ability to communicate in a group setting) and Psychological disadvantages (such as the pressure to compare oneself to others on these platforms and become distracted).
4. There is a negative impact of Social Media usage on a student's Psychological well-being: There is a large percentage of students that suffer from Moderate to High levels of Stress; Low to Average levels of Self-esteem; Sleep Disturbance and Negative Psychological impacts. These impacts indicate that Heavy usage creates Emotional strain.
5. Academic Focus is decreased for Heavy Social Media Users: Many students have reported that they have either a Weak or Moderate Academic focus as a result of the amount of time they spend using Social Media. Therefore, either through direct distraction or indirect interference with productivity, students experience lower levels of Academic focus due to their Heavy usage of Social Media.
6. Students utilize society media: differently perform academically better than those who primarily use the media for social entertainment.
7. A student's negative emotional experiences: due to comparison with others contributes negatively to that student's motivation to achieve academic success, and therefore the student show less motivation to achieve, and less persistence and effort toward achieving educational goals.
8. Exposure to two types of content has advantages and disadvantages to students: Any

student who focuses on watching primarily educational related videos have more successful academic habits, while those students who are engaged in primarily watching entertainment related videos suffer from avoidance and procrastination.

9. A student's emotional health: Therefore influence how much enjoyment he/she feels from using social media and achieving academically. Therefore, psychological issues such as stress, low self-esteem, and emotional imbalance define a student's success in utilizing social media for educational success.

10. Overall students gain experience from social media: The findings indicate that students can gain from the experience of using social media in a positive manner and have some experiences that can create difficulty for the student in academic performance.

Conclusion

While the most prominent conclusion of this work is that the usage of social media has a multidimensional and significant impact on both the mental health and the academic performance of students, the authors stress that moderate and academically based use is beneficial. Such usage enables students to communicate, to conduct research and to collaborate. Excessive use of social media for entertainment purposes creates difficulties for the student as far as mental health and may create issues such as anxiety, stress, poor self-image, sleep disturbances and emotional instability. In turn, these psychological difficulties impact the student's academic focus, productivity and academic success. Ultimately, the author concluded that the relationship between social media and academic performance cannot be assessed as purely positive or negative. Instead, it is contingent upon the intent of the user, the length of use and the user's level of emotional sensitivity. The authors also note that students should be taught to develop a balance of digital usage and to use social media responsibly by way of educational interventions.

Recommendations

From the results and evidential support the following recommendations are made:

1. Implementing a Curriculum That Encourages Digital Literacy. Educational institutions should develop and implement a data literacy program that

promotes the safe, responsible, and academic use of social media among students.

2. Encouraging Healthy Digital Habits. Students should learn ways to set boundaries on their screen time and establish some guidelines, such as:

- Establishing a daily maximum time limit
- Utilizing apps that assist with study breaks
- Emphasizing academic material rather than entertainment

3. Schools and Universities Must Enhance Mental Health Infrastructure. Schools and universities must develop and provide through their established mental health support systems:

- Access to mental health professionals (e.g. psychologists) to provide counselling and therapy
- Support for managing stress
- Information sessions on mental and emotional well-being

4. Expand Educational Use of Social Media.

Teachers can assist in promoting educational content through the following tools:

- Encouraging the creation of study groups on WhatsApp
- Establishing Facebook Communities for classroom interactions
- Developing academic playlists on YouTube

Encouraging the use of social media for educational purposes helps reduce the likelihood of students developing patterns that lead to negative consequences from using social media.

5. Parents and Caregivers Need to Monitor Their Children's Digital Behaviours.

Parental involvement is critical when guiding students toward responsible digital engagement, especially for younger students.

6. Policies that all institutions should create to present to their students Good and Positive Digital Environments.

Some Examples of This are:

- Policies that Limit the Use of Non-academic Phones in Classrooms

- Anti-Cyberbullying Policies
- Policies for Establishing Digital Discipline

7. Institutions should Encourage All Students to Access More Educational Material.

The large number of educational resources on each of the various social media platforms provide students with an opportunity to find and follow profiles that are related to learning, science and self-development.

8. Raise Awareness among Students about the Impact of Social Media on Self-esteem

Raise awareness among students about the impact of social media on self-esteem and, encourage students to avoid have to deal with unproductive patterns through raising awareness and drogram Development.

9. Conduct Further Research to Study

- Group Differences of Impact of Social Media on Gender
- Changes Over Time of Digital Behavior Patterns
- Impact of Different Types of Social Media Platforms
- How Well Digital Interventions Work

10. Promote Healthy Digital Detox by Motivating Students to Increase Their Digital Detox Frequency.

Time away from social media provides a break from the mental burden of following other's digital lives and helps improve academic concentration and focus.

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